

EcoLink: A Digital Platform for Sustainability, Community Engagement, and Waste Management

Pedro Gonçalves Prazeres¹, Yasmim Bezerra Oliveira Altoé¹, Davi Cunha Vanderlei¹, Simone Borges Simão Monteiro¹, Iara Gomes Andrade¹

¹ Production Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Brasilia, Brasilia, Brazil

Email: pedroprazer98@yahoo.com.br, bezerrayasmim7@gmail.com, 211038333@aluno.unb.br, simone_simao@yahoo.com.br, 170012484@aluno.unb.br

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Abstract

The growing awareness of sustainability has driven the development of technological solutions aimed at centralizing and enhancing sustainable initiatives. The EcoLink app emerges as a digital platform designed to integrate information, foster community engagement, and encourage eco-friendly practices, promoting accessibility and positive environmental impact. The project was proposed by students participating in the Egalitarian project, under the ERASMUS+ program funded by the European Union. This international program seeks sustainable solutions for global challenges by connecting students and professors from different countries and applying an active learning methodology in project development. The research follows a qualitative, exploratory, and applied approach, focusing on three key aspects. Initially, a study on sustainability, conscious disposal, and recycling was conducted within the Brasília community, engaging over 230 participants. This study enabled the identification of users' specific needs, allowing for the development of personas, brand identity, and the structuring of high-level functional requirements for the app. This article aims to present the EcoLink modules, which include: i) Marketplace, connecting consumers with certified businesses that offer sustainable products; ii) Information hub, functioning as a repository of specialized sustainability content, enabling waste pickers to educate the public on proper waste disposal; iii) Reuse and recycling, facilitating the donation and collection of recyclable materials, ensuring their proper allocation to sustainable initiatives; and iv) Community, promoting social interaction through experience-sharing and access to eco-friendly events. The next steps involve app development, consolidating the planned features and ensuring their implementation for the target audience. The EcoLink app aims to democratize access to sustainability, strengthen the green economy, and foster collective engagement, establishing itself as a key solution for environmental awareness and social transformation.

Keywords: Egalitarian Project, Digital Platform, Community Engagement, Conscious Disposal, Active Learning.

1 Introduction

Contemporary society is characterized by an exacerbated consumption model, in which the creation of false needs drives the uncontrolled acquisition of goods, resulting in a growing production of municipal solid waste (Almeida et al., 2020). This scenario has become one of the central issues on global sustainability agendas, being a complex and multifaceted problem. Factors such as rapid population growth, the widespread generation of non-recyclable materials, and inadequate management practices exacerbate the situation, leading to negative environmental impacts, such as biodiversity loss and the intensification of climate change (Guimarães, 2019).

The advancement of digital technologies has profoundly changed the way information is disseminated and absorbed, expanding access to knowledge and facilitating environmental awareness. Environmental education plays a critical role in this process, as without clear guidelines and accessible knowledge, concern for the environment often fails to translate into concrete actions (Da Silva Lima et al., 2020).

The lack of centralized and accurate information about sustainable initiatives hinders both individuals interested in contributing and initiatives that depend on support and visibility, highlighting the need for platforms that connect society to viable and accessible solutions (Aquino; Castilho Jr; Pires, 2009). In this

context, higher education institutions and research centers have played a significant role in developing solutions focused on environmental management, promoting projects that integrate education, technology, and sustainability (Brasi et al., 2019).

The Egalitarian project, an Erasmus+ initiative of the European Union led by students, aims to develop innovative solutions for waste management and the improvement of waste pickers' quality of life in Brasília, aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda. The project encourages collaborative work among students from different countries and disciplines—mostly from engineering and computer science—with support from professors and academic institutions. One of the main goals of Egalitarian is to create digital solutions to optimize waste management and enhance the social impact of these initiatives (Egalitarian, 2025).

Thus, the EcoLink app emerges with the goal of integrating information, promoting environmental education, and stimulating the circular economy through interaction among users, waste pickers, and companies. This article aims to analyze the potential impact of EcoLink and present the stages that guided its development. Furthermore, the functionalities of each module of the platform will be detailed, highlighting how its tools contribute to social engagement, environmental awareness, and the adoption of sustainable practices. EcoLink, therefore, positions itself as an accessible and innovative resource capable of driving meaningful transformations and promoting a more responsible and conscious consumption model.

2 Theoretical Framework

The Egalitarian project is an initiative that seeks to encourage participants to work in multicultural teams, addressing real-world challenges related to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda. The project's proposal aims to stimulate the development and implementation of innovative solutions focused on optimizing solid waste management and improving the working conditions and quality of life of waste pickers in Brasília (Egalitarian, 2025).

As part of the European Union's Erasmus+ program, Egalitarian is based on the use of active learning methodologies, particularly Project-Based Learning (PjBL), an educational approach in which students occupy a central role in the learning process and are encouraged to solve authentic problems in collaborative contexts. The PjBL methodology is characterized by promoting practical problem-solving while simultaneously fostering the development of essential scientific skills. According to Nurhidayah et al. (2021), students engaged in PjBL acquire competencies to address scientific questions through hypothesis formulation, planning and conducting experiments, as well as making careful observations and performing rigorous data analysis.

To meet the labor market demand for professionals with solid knowledge in project management, the University of Brasília has structured the Production Engineering program around seven courses called Production Systems Projects (PSPs), taught sequentially from the fourth to the tenth semester. These courses, grounded in the PjBL methodology, aim to develop both specific technical competencies and essential transversal skills in students, such as leadership, proactive management, effective communication, and teamwork capabilities (Monteiro et al., 2017).

Another key aspect of the Egalitarian project's approach lies in the development of innovative digital solutions. In this context, students are encouraged to explore contemporary technological tools applied to sustainability and efficient waste management. Working in interdisciplinary groups, participants develop digital solutions that seek to optimize key processes such as selective waste collection and the productive inclusion of waste pickers. The replicability of these solutions is a critical factor, allowing successful initiatives in Brasília to be adapted and implemented in other global contexts. Additionally, the emphasis on digital development enables

participating students to acquire skills valued in the contemporary job market, such as process automation, data analysis, and the use of collaborative digital platforms.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research classification

This is an applied research project, as it aims to generate knowledge directed toward solving a practical problem. According to Dresch et al. (2015), applied research seeks to create a direct impact on reality, unlike purely theoretical research, which aims to expand knowledge without immediate application. The method adopted in this research is inductive, as it begins with the observation of specific situations to build broader knowledge. The starting point was the analysis of the challenges faced by recyclable material collectors and the community in Brasília regarding waste management. Based on this information, a technological solution applicable to the studied context was structured.

According to Prodanov and De Freitas (2013), exploratory research is appropriate when the goal is to gain greater familiarity with a problem and to structure hypotheses or conceptual models. In the case of EcoLink, the study was conducted to map user needs and understand how a digital platform can contribute to promoting sustainable solutions and environmental education, thus adopting an exploratory character. Regarding the research approach, this is a qualitative study, as it aims to understand users' perceptions, behaviors, and expectations related to practices and the use of sustainable platforms. As described by Creswell et al. (2017), instead of using quantitative, statistics-based approaches, this research prioritizes the analysis of form, interviews, and observations to support the development of the application. The development of EcoLink is considered a case study, as it was analyzed within the specific context of the city of Brasília and its solid waste management network, allowing for a detailed examination of local challenges and opportunities.

3.2 Research structure

The research was structured in sequential stages, ensuring a systematic process for the development of the EcoLink platform. The main phases that guided the study are described below, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Stages of the research, Developed by the authors (2025)

In the first stage, a comprehensive literature review was conducted on topics related to sustainability, circular economy, waste management, and digital platforms. This stage was fundamental in building the theoretical foundation of the study. Data collection took place in the second stage, during which a form was administered to over 230 participants, including community members, recyclable material collectors, and environmental specialists. The goal of this phase was to understand the main challenges related to sustainable practices and expectations regarding a digital solution. Based on the analysis of the collected data, representative personas of the application's user profiles were created, helping to define the user experience and develop EcoLink's

visual identity. Drawing on the identified needs, the functional requirements of the app were established to ensure that its features addressed the demands mapped during the research, as well as to define the user journey flow. The main modules of EcoLink were then defined: i) Marketplace, to connect consumers with sustainable businesses; ii) Information Hub, to provide educational content; iii) Reuse and Recycling, to facilitate donations and collection of recyclable materials; and iv) Community, to promote sustainable interactions and events. Finally, in the last stage, wireframes and interactive prototypes were created to visualize and test EcoLink's usability, allowing for adjustments before the start of technical development.

4 Results and Discussion

To clearly understand the context in which the application is inserted, a survey was conducted through a form consisting of 24 questions, structured into three main sections: Demographic Analysis, Interest in Sustainability, Conscious Disposal and Reuse, and Applications Related to Sustainability. The survey was applied in the Federal District and received 230 responses. The results provided an understanding of the population's interest in sustainability issues, with approximately 80% of respondents stating they were interested in the topic. However, 204 participants indicated that they were unaware of any application or platform that centralizes sustainable information in the region, highlighting the relevance of creating EcoLink. Additionally, the responses collected allowed for the identification of the themes most valued by potential users, such as locating nearby recycling points, practical sustainability tips, places to buy sustainable products, and information on reuse and recycling. These insights were crucial in structuring the application's modules, guiding the development of features aligned with the preferences and needs of the population. Based on the data collected and analyzed, it was also possible to define the personas that guide the project.

This preliminary foundation drove significant advancements in the development of EcoLink in the second half of 2024. Among the key results, a clear definition of the application's modular structure stands out, organized into four main areas: Marketplace, Information Hub, Community, and Reuse and Recycling. Additionally, the functional requirements of each module were defined and detailed by the PSP5 team, ensuring that the features were aligned with EcoLink's goals, as shown in Figure 2.

Marketplace					
Descrição:	Um espaço exclusivo para empresas certificadas venderem produtos sustentáveis de diversas categorias, conectando consumidores conscientes a opções que promovem impacto positivo no meio ambiente.				
Usuários					
Tela 1: Home Marketplace		Prioridade: Must Have			
Ideia Geral: Apresenta produtos sustentáveis em destaque, categorias principais e lojas certificadas. É a porta de entrada para o usuário explorar produtos e marcas.					
Requisitos	User Journey	Elementos visuais	Interações	Observação	Priorização
Produtos e Lojas	O usuário acessa a tela inicial e visualiza produtos em destaque, lojas recomendadas, principais categorias e sugestões personalizadas com base no comportamento de navegação.	Carrusel de produtos, lojas com nome e logo.	O usuário pode clicar em produtos ou lojas para acessar mais informações.	Referências: Méliuz, Nubank (sessão shopping), Banco Inter (sessão Shopping), Ifood, Enjoei	Must Have
Busca de produtos, lojas ou categorias	O usuário utiliza a barra de busca para localizar produtos ou lojas específicas, digitando palavras-chave e recebendo resultados instantâneos	Barra de busca fixa no topo com placeholder "Buscar por produtos ou lojas".	O usuário digita um termo e recebe sugestões ou resultados ao pressionar "Enter".	Quando o usuário clicar, é redirecionado para a Página de Pesquisa	Should Have
Notificações e Promoções	O usuário visualiza banners de promoções e notificações importantes na página inicial, clicando neles para obter mais informações.	Banner fixo ou rotativo com informações sobre promoções ou novidades do marketplace.	O usuário pode clicar no banner para explorar mais detalhes sobre as promoções exibidas.	Referências: Méliuz, Nubank (sessão shopping), Banco Inter (sessão Shopping), Ifood, Enjoei	Should Have
Tela 2: Página da Loja		Prioridade: Must Have			
Ideia Geral: Mostra os detalhes gerais da loja, como logo, descrições e os produtos disponíveis. Permite					

Figure 2. Example of the detailed functional requirements of the EcoLink modules, Developed by the authors (2025)

To enable visualization of the platform's structure and simulate the user experience, the PSP2 team of the 2024.2 semester developed the first interface prototypes for each of the modules highlighted earlier.

4.1 Modules

4.1.1 Marketplace

The Marketplace module was designed as an exclusive space for certified companies to sell sustainable products from various categories. This environment aims to connect conscious consumers with purchasing options that promote a positive environmental impact and encourage responsible consumption practices. The goal is to ensure that all products available on the application meet pre-established sustainability criteria, strengthening user trust and encouraging the choice of environmentally friendly alternatives.

Figure 3: Marketplace screens prototyped by PSP2, Developed by the authors (2024)

As shown in Figure 3, the Marketplace module displays featured sustainable products, main categories, and certified stores, functioning as the entry point for the user to explore the marketplace. The requirements include product and store visualization, smart product search, and promotional notifications, promoting navigation and engagement with relevant offers. The purchasing journey is facilitated with a shopping cart, delivery and payment forms, order summary, and a simple and intuitive checkout process.

4.1.2 Community

The Community module was conceived as an interactive space that connects users and organizations engaged in sustainability issues, such as recyclable material collectors. Through videos, comments, and interactions, participants will be able to share experiences, discuss ideas, and promote initiatives that contribute to strengthening the community. This environment aims to create a support and collaboration network, encouraging user engagement and expanding the reach of actions in favor of the environment. It is important to highlight the relevance of the module, as the process of sustainable mobilization can be carried out through digital means.

Figure 4: Community screens prototyped by PSP2, Developed by the authors (2024)

As shown in Figure 4, the Community module integrates functional requirements that promote the exchange of experiences among users, such as the display of posts, interaction buttons (like, comment, share), creation of publications, and advanced search for content and profiles engaged in sustainability.

4.1.3 Information Hub

The Information Hub module has as its main objective to centralize the dissemination of content on sustainability, offering users easy access to reliable and up-to-date information. In this space, specialized magazines, institutions, and experts will be able to share news, articles, and technical reports related to the environment, sustainable practices, and related topics. By gathering this material in a single environment, the application aims to promote awareness and broaden users' knowledge about the challenges and solutions for environmental preservation.

Figure 5: Information Hub screens prototyped by PSP2, Developed by the authors (2024)

As shown in Figure 5, the Information Hub module gathers content on sustainability in a space where authors can create, edit, and manage publications with images, categories, and engagement statistics. Users can access full articles, share content, and explore related materials. Navigation is optimized with features such as drafts, text formatting, and thematic filters.

4.1.4 Reuse and Recycling

The Reuse and Recycling module aims to facilitate the process of donating and collecting recyclable material to ensure that resources are allocated to sustainable initiatives, such as recycling cooperatives. In this environment, a map of the Federal District will be displayed, and collection points will be highlighted to show all the locations for receiving material in the region. This module seeks to ensure that the donation and disposal process is carried out consciously so that organizations receive the appropriate materials, properly organized.

Due to prioritization during development, the requirements for the module have not yet been raised. However, its development is planned for the next stages of the project, given its importance to the platform's proposal and the impact it will have on sustainable initiatives. Therefore, by breaking down each module of EcoLink, it was possible to validate the initial proposal, identify improvements for each module, and ensure that design decisions are aligned with the project's goals and the target audience's needs. The results obtained so far represent an important milestone in the development of EcoLink, establishing a solid foundation for the next phases of implementation and testing with users. The project remains aligned with the purpose of creating a digital tool capable of strengthening sustainable practices, promoting access to qualified information, and stimulating the creation of a community engaged in environmental preservation.

5 Conclusion

The integration of digitalization and sustainability carried out by the Egalitarian project not only fosters positive environmental impacts but also empowers students in the use of digital technologies aimed at improving the quality of life in vulnerable communities. This initiative reinforces the commitment of young people to socio-environmental transformation.

The adoption of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) in university courses was crucial both for the conception and structuring of the EcoLink application. This methodology enabled a practical and interdisciplinary approach, encouraging students to actively participate from the ideation phase to detailed planning and the definition of technical requirements for the application. Through this process, it was possible to systematize research and organize the essential artifacts for the implementation of the solution, ensuring a consistent theoretical foundation aligned with the real needs of the target audience. In this way, PjBL confirmed its effectiveness as a pedagogical strategy capable of bridging theory and practice, strengthening students' preparation to face real challenges and develop innovative solutions focused on environmental and social issues.

The results obtained indicate that EcoLink holds significant potential to centralize relevant information on sustainable practices, stimulate community engagement, and facilitate interaction between consumers, recyclers, and companies committed to sustainability.

As a recommendation for future work, it is suggested to begin the practical development of the application by creating a Minimum Viable Product (MVP). This approach will allow for the validation of the initial assumptions of the proposal and promote iterative improvements based on real user feedback. Additionally, the importance of establishing strategic partnerships with companies and institutions in the sustainable sector is emphasized to expand the reach of EcoLink and ensure its effective implementation. In this way, the project positions itself

as a promising digital tool to stimulate conscious consumption models and facilitate access to innovative sustainable solutions.

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